

Canary Islands Data Management Plan

Version 0.2

EMSO ERIC
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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Author(s)
0.1	28/11/2023	First draft	
0.2	24/01/2023	Data Collection definition	María Díaz, Andrés Cianca

DMP Canary Islands

Dataset Overview	
Dataset Title	The European Station for Time-series in the Ocean, Canary Islands (ESTOC)
Dataset Description	<p>ESTOC has significantly contributed to scientific research by time series data on the biogeochemical processes of the ocean. Three distinct datasets are generated based on the observation platforms employed, encompassing oceanographic vessels, fixed structures, and autonomous vehicles. The ship-based dataset, initiated in 1994, encompasses a broad spectrum of oceanographic variables, including temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH, chlorophyll, and more. The mooring dataset, commencing in 1991, began with a sediment trap deployment and evolved into a hydrographical mooring in 1994, later replaced by a multidisciplinary mooring in 2002. The current dataset collects atmospheric and oceanographic data at three depths: surface, 80 meters, and 150 meters. Glider datasets capture observations up to 1000 meters deep from the coastal observatory at PLOCAN and the ESTOC station.</p> <p>These variables are routinely monitored and are essential for understanding the dynamics of the ocean's biogeochemical processes and the effects of climate change on marine ecosystems. Sensors deployed on buoys, drifting floats, moored stations and autonomous vehicles collect time-series data of these parameters, allowing for the analysis of trends and variations over time.</p>

Data Collection
<p>The ESTOC station is an oceanic observatory located at approximately 29° 10'N latitude and 15° 30'W longitude, at a depth of 3,610 meters, to the north of the Canary Islands, serving as a reference for the Central-Eastern Atlantic. This station generates long-term meteorological and oceanographic time-series based on the observation platforms employed, including oceanographic vessels, fixed structures, and autonomous vehicles. It was established in February 1994 to investigate changes in ocean stratification, large-scale circulation, and biogeochemical cycles affecting carbon flux between the atmosphere and the ocean.</p> <p>The ESTOC station employs a variety of platforms and methods to collect oceanographic data:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mooring Platform: <p>The mooring platform has been utilized for continuous data collection through instruments anchored to the seabed that record various biogeochemical parameters. Initially, the moorings were sediment traps and hydrographic instruments. The former was used to capture specific fluxes, while the latter was employed to determine currents through several sensors at different depths and Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCP). Later, biogeochemical sensors measuring dissolved oxygen, pH,</p>

pCO₂, and nitrates were added. These moorings have enabled measurements at multiple depths, providing valuable data on ocean currents and chemical properties.

- Ship-based Programs:

The ship-based programs include in situ sampling with vertical profiles using CTDs/Rosette and Niskin bottles to collect water samples at different depths. These measurements provide detailed profiles of temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and other nutrients. Additionally, temperature probes and drifting buoys have been launched to support NOAA's global program. The vessels also played a crucial role in carrying out oceanographic campaigns that produced additional CTD profiles for research at the ESTOC site.

- Autonomous Glider Missions:

Since 2012, autonomous glider missions have been incorporated into the observation program. These autonomous vehicles are equipped with CTDs and biogeochemical sensors and can perform missions lasting about 21 days, profiling the water column down to approximately 1000 meters deep. They follow a triangular trajectory to the ESTOC station, providing valuable data on the spatial and temporal variability in the water column. Gliders are used to supplement stationary observations, offering a more dynamic and detailed picture of oceanic processes in the region

	MOORING PLATFORM		SHIP-BASED PROGRAM		GLIDER MISSIONS
	ATMOSPHERE	OCEAN	WATER COL. SAMPLING	DRIFTER/ XBT	WATER COL. SAMPLING
PARAMETERS	TEMPERATURE PRESSURE REL. HUMIDITY PAR WIND SPEED WIND DIRECTION	TEMPERATURE SALINITY CURRENTS DISSOL. OXYGEN pH pCO ₂ CHLOROPHYLL DIN PON POC PARTICLE FLUX SOUND	TEMPERATURE SALINITY DISSOL. OXYGEN pH ALCALINITY CHLOROPHYLL DIC DIN DIP DIS PIGMENTS	TEMPERATURE CURRENTS	TEMPERATURE SALINITY CURRENTS DISSOL. OXYGEN CHLOROPHYLL
RESOLUTION	REAL TIME; Hourly DELAYED MODE; 900s.	REAL TIME; Hourly DELAYED MODE; 900s. pH, pCO ₂ and DIN: 3 times per day PON, POC and PF: 1 time per week.	1994 – 2003: Monthly 2003- Present: 2 – 4 times per year	1994 – 2003: Monthly 2003- today: 2 – 4 times per year	: 2 – 4 times per year 21 days per mission
TIME RANGE	2003- Present	1994- 2002 hydrography 2002- Present: Multidisciplinary	1994- present (Carbon parameters from 1996 and pigments from 2008)	1997- present	2012- present

Figure 1. Summary of the various datasets obtained from the observation programs conducted at ESTOC until 2021.

The oceanic observatory ESTOC, maintained by PLOCAN-IEO-ULPGC in the Canary Islands, is part of the European EMSO-ERIC and ICOS-ERIC infrastructures.

Documentation and Metadata

The metadata are standardized into netCDF files, following the format conventions and standards defined by EMSO, as described in the EMSO ERIC Data Management.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

PLOCAN observatory data is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Storage and Backup

All data are secured on a long-term archiving system. Data are stored in an open and self-descriptive format.

Selection and Preservation

All datasets are long term preserved.

The data are stored into PLOCAN database.

PLOCAN Observatory Data Policy complies with the European Directive on Infrastructures for Spatial Information, the GEOSS Data Sharing Principles, EMODNET data ingestion policy and more generally FAIR4 principles.

Data Sharing

PLOCAN's monitoring experience provides a range of data routinely obtained through its facilities and equipment. This data is available to users, openly, and are accessed through PLOCAN's website.

Datasets are free available: <http://data.plocan.eu/thredds/catalog.html> and ERDDAP (under development).

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Responsibilities and Resources

Data is provided as-is, without any warranty, express or implied. While efforts are made to ensure accuracy, completeness, and timeliness, PLOCAN does not guarantee fitness for a particular purpose. Users are advised to independently verify the data and use it at their own risk. PLOCAN disclaims any liability for errors, omissions, or inaccuracies in the data and is not responsible for any damages arising from its use.

